

bacteria⁷. It was, therefore, considered of interest to carry out systematic investigations on this plant.

The present paper deals with the isolation and structural elucidation of the active principle responsible for antibacterial activity from the petroleum ether extract of the leaves of this plant.

Experimental

Green leaves of the plant were collected from Terai-region (Pantnagar, District Naini Tal, India), dried in shade and finely powdered. The powder was Soxhletted with petroleum ether (60°-80°) for about 24 hr. The extract was left overnight in a refrigerator when crystals separated out, which were dissolved in ether and charcoalised. The ethereal solution on concentration afforded colourless crystals which were recrystallised from an ether-alcohol mixture (4:1, V/V) to afford colourless shining crystals melting at 100°-101° (Found: C, 66.60%; H, 7.05%; C₁₇H₂₂O₃ requires: C, 66.65%; H, 7.25%). The yield of the compound ranges from 0.5 to 0.7% based on the dry weight of the leaves.

The I.R. spectrum of this compound indicated the presence of a γ -Lactonic carbonyl (1756 cm⁻¹), an acetate carbonyl (1735 cm⁻¹) and a ketonic carbonyl (1721 cm⁻¹). The m.p. was found to be identical with Xanthumin⁸, but different from the one reported for Xanthinin⁹. The identity of this compound as Xanthumin was further established by mixed melting point. R_f and I.R. spectrum were found to be identical with an authentic sample.

It is interesting to observe that Xanthumin is present in both the Indian and Japanese varieties of *X. strumarium* while Xanthinin has been found to be present in Canadian *X. strumarium*.

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Thermodynamic Formation Constants of Metal Chelates of Sulphadimethoxin Salicylaldimine

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IN continuation of our previous communications^{1,2} herein we describe potentiometric studies on complexes of sulphadimethoxin salicylaldimine (SUDMSA) with Copper (II), Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II) at 25°. The Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique^{3,4} as used by Irving and Rossotti⁵ has been applied to determine the protonation constant of the ligand and the formation constants of complexes. The log *k* values have been computed by least square method. Free energy changes and probability errors have also been evaluated.

These values at an ionic strength ($\mu = 0.2M$) are summarised in Table I.

Table I						
Ion	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log $\frac{K_1}{K_2}$	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$	σ
H			log $\beta^H = 6.2$			
Cu(II)	5.50	3.42	8.92	2.08	-12.22	±.0005
Ni(II)	5.10	2.72	7.82	2.38	-10.66	±.001
Co(II)	4.03	2.22	6.24	1.80	-8.55	±.010

From the values of stability constants of the metal chelates the order is Cu > Ni > Co. This is in accordance with Irving and Williams.⁶

The large difference between successive formation constants may be attributed to the greater steric hindrance offered by SUDMSA as compared with the coordinated water molecule.

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